

PREVALENCE OF CERVICAL HUMAN PAPILLOMA VIRUS INFECTION AMONG WOMEN IN BAYELSA STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

This study on the prevalence of cervical human papilloma virus was carried out in Niger Delta, Bayelsa State, Nigeria. Four hundred and fifty (450) consenting sexually active females were recruited. The objective was to determine the prevalence of cervical human papilloma virus (HPV). Human papilloma viruses are small non enveloped icosahedral DNA viruses that replicate in the nucleus of squamous epithelial cells. 4.2% prevalence was recorded with zero prevalence between 10-29 years and least between 50-59 years of age. There exists a relationship between HPV and cervical dysplasia. Therefore, awareness and preventive vaccination is advocated in Bayelsa State to prevent future occurrence of cervical cancer.

KEYWORDS: cervical cancer, DNA viruses, Bayelsa State , sexually active, vaccination

INTRODUCTION

Human papilloma virus is a small non enveloped icosahedral DNA virus that replicates in the nucleus of squamous epithelial cells (Parkin et al., 2006). They are called papilloma virus because certain strains may cause warts or papilloma which are benign (non-cancerous) tumors (Kumar et al., 2007).

Genital human papilloma virus is the most common sexually transmitted infection (CDC, 2009). It is divided into low risk and high risk strains. HPV-6 and HPV-11 (low risk) causes condylomata acuminata while types 16 and 18 which together causes about 70% of cervical cancers (Munoz et al., 2004) Having many sexual partners is a risk factor for HPV infection together with other risk factors such as smoking, multiparity, early onset of sexual intercourse, oral contraceptive and Human Immuno deficiency virus increases an individual's chance of contracting cervical cancer.

The world wide prevalence in 2002 was estimated at 52% out of 561,200 new cancers. (Parkin, 2006). Approximately 20 million are infected with HPV (David and Alison, 2009). In Nigeria like most other under developed nations, the incidence is still on the increase due to lack of adequate screening, programmes, follow up and vaccines. However, the Government of Nigeria and that of Bayelsa State have started the catch them young initiatives through immunization. The aim of this research was to document the prevalence of HPV in Bayelsa State .

MATERIAL AND METHODS

STUDY AREA

Bayelsa State is located within Lat 4°15'N and Lat 5°23' south and Long. 5°22' and 6°45' East. It is bounded on North West by Delta State , Rivers State on East and Atlantic Ocean on the southern part. The study area is over populated with influx of commercial sex workers for greener pastures being an oil rich zone. Finally based on 1991 census it has a population of 1.2m people.

SELECTION, COLLECTION AND PREPARATION OF SAMPLES

All consenting sexually active females between 10-75 years of age attending designated health centres for various ailments within the period of study were recruited including those with symptoms suggesting STD and cervical cancers. Cervical smears (pap smear) were collected from 450 women using disposable speculum and Ayres spatula and grease free slides. Standard Papanicolaou staining technique was adopted using Harris Hematoxylin as nuclear stain, EA-50 and modified O-G-6 for cytoplasm (11). The slides show a range of green, blue and pinkish cytoplasm with blue nuclear smear that contained multinucleated giant cells, koilocytes,

dykarypsis, nuclear-halo were marked as positive for Human papuloma virus. Standard monographs were equally used for comparison.

RESULTS

Table 1: The relationship between cervical human papuloma virus and cervical dysplasia

Age (yr)	No examined	Cervical HPV (%)	Cervical dysplasia
10-19	323	5 (1.1)	14 (3.1)
50-above	127	14 (3.1)	9 (2.0)
Total	450 (225±138)	19 (9.5±6)	23 (11.5±4)

p=0.05, x2=5.014

Table2 Distribution of HPV, microbes and fungal infection among subjects studied.

Age (yr)	No examined	% HPV	% Microbes	% Fungi
10-19	110	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)
20-29	95	0 (0.0)	2(22.3)	3(33.3)
30-39	112	3 (15.7)	5(55.6)	3(33.2)
40-49	105	2 (10.5)	0 (0.0)	2(22.3)
50-59	74	9(47.3)	0(0.0)	1(11.1)
60-69	38	3(15.7)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)
70>	15	2 (10.5)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)

DISCUSSION

The prevalence of cervical human papiloma virus was 4.2% among subjects studied while cervical dyplasia-both low grade and high grade accounted for 5.1%.The relationship between HPV and dysplasia was tested and found significant p< 0.05 and x2= 5.014, Table 1. However, HPV prevalence of 15% prevalence has been reported in Irun-urban of Ibadan Nigeria (Parkin 2006). Hillard documented an estimate of 14% to more than 90%. Khan (2009) equally reported 1.4% in Spain . Research attributes these differences due to strains tested for and method used. Schiller (2010) reported a highest prevalence in 20-24 years and lowest in 50-57 years of age as against a zero prevalence recorded between 10-29 years of age and highest in 50-59, and this is attributed to the ability of the immune response to clear the infection beyond detectable levels among the age of 10-29 compared to 50-59 years with declining immune competence.

There is a strong relationship exiting between the microbes 2(1.2±1.8) , fungi (1.3±1.4). and HPV infection

CONCLUSION

This finding shows that women in Bayelsa State should be considered for close screening and follow up and preferably coloscopic referral. This will help reduce the emergence of cervical cancers. Awareness on the modes of transmission of cervical human Papiloma Virus should be given a frontal attack while immunization response should be studied

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